

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION”

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MODERN RESEARCH IN THE FIELD OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES TEACHING METHODS, LINGUISTICS, PEDAGOGY

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Annotation. The article is an analysis of current areas of methodological research in the field of methods of teaching English as a foreign language. The main feature of modern methodology is attention to problem solving, related to the language acquisition of each student. Practice has convincingly proven that in the educational process there is no minor, unimportant components. Hence, it is necessary to optimize not individual, but all links of the educational process, which should ultimately lead to the creation of an adequate psychophysiological structure of training, taking into account various social, sociolinguistic, psychological and other factors.

Key words: linguistics, methodology, pedagogy, languages, teaching.

For millions of people on our planet, English is a window to the world of universal human culture and science, a tool for interethnic communication.

In modern society, specialists from various branches of science, need new information in the area of their specialty and for this purpose refer to various sources of information, mainly in English language, because England was and remains the most printing and translating country, and a huge part of educational literature is still available in English language.

The number of English language learners is increasing every year. Interest to the English language is determined by objective factors. It's dynamic development of European countries, increasing its importance and role in all areas of development modern world, the transformation of English into one of the most informative world languages. It plays an important role in sharing experiences, knowledge, in the development of advanced culture.

English is the language of international cooperation, the language of progress.

When choosing English as an object of study, one should highlight the following motives:

- interest in the country of the language being studied, its history, modernity, development of culture, science, economics;
- linguistic and aesthetic interest in the English language;
- interest in personal contacts with native speakers.

Knowledge of English will allow citizens of different countries to satisfy their life, professional, spiritual, ideological needs, expand their ideas about the world. In

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this regard, the question of methods in teaching English for foreigners becomes more relevant. Currently approximately 16 methods of teaching a second language are currently used. Consequently, a stage has come when it is necessary to properly understand the essence of the methods used and in current terminology, find out in under what conditions this or that teaching method is most promising, outline ways to modify the method used in order to improve it and, finally, obtain information about methods that have not yet become widespread known and are at the stage of experimental testing [1].

The methodology has become a more self-sufficient and comprehensive science, thanks to the creation of educational dictionaries, descriptions of communication programs competencies for various categories of students studied individual characteristics (cognitive operations and actions) of language mastery [2]. Currently, variable learning technology has been developed with using laser-computer complexes, representing the student has the right to choose, ensuring independent types of work.

Teaching a foreign language has its own specifics, different from specifics of teaching the native language. When teaching native language, choice of communicative techniques depending on educational goals are determined only by communicative specificity, the significance of communicative techniques for specific purposes of this form of teaching. When teaching a foreign language, to the communicative significance is added purely linguistic moment - the need to master the system of a foreign language in particularly those elements that are different from the students' native language. This is where characterized communication techniques come to the rescue. They make it possible to combine training in speech situations with practicing linguistic principles: for example, training in expressing reason and justification connect with the assimilation of causal prepositions and conjunctions as part of circumstances and additional reasons. The meaning of functional-semantic presentation material is that simultaneously with the presentation of grammatical material to begin to develop speech skills, providing the student with speech samples. This linking of grammar with communicative techniques is an effective method of shortening the path from the language system to the speech system activities. However, speech patterns perform their function only when the presence of certain conditions, in particular:

1. Samples must be accompanied, where necessary, by commentary. conditions for their use.
2. The presentation of samples must be accompanied by a system of exercises.

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION”

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3. It is necessary to constantly develop students' motivation to master speech samples.

What is usually overlooked in traditional teaching methods is the fact that in the real educational process the teacher and student see practical goals from different angles. To avoid this inconsistency of educational goals, the teacher must correlate them with communicative and cognitive interests and needs of students, with their potential abilities, real capabilities, features of training, etc.

It is necessary to use a differentiated approach to supply educational language and speech material. The following ways of presenting new educational material may be proposed to the learner [3]:

1. clearly illustrated
2. gaming
3. inductive
4. deductive
5. imitative.
6. contrastive

A stimulator of intellectual-mental and communicative-cognitive activity of students in English classes is a clearly thought-out system of verbal and mental tasks that should evoke the speaker's desire to express his attitude to phenomena, facts, reality. In essence, the entire process of communication consists of solving speech-thinking and communicative problems.

Methods of teaching foreign languages should be based on data from such sciences as linguistics, psychology, linguacultural studies, pedagogy.

Linguacultural studies form a specific part of the content teaching English as a foreign language – linguistic and cultural studies information.

The concept of linguacultural studies includes such non-verbal components of communication such as the language of facial expressions, gestures, new rules for a foreigner and norms of behavior adopted by native English speakers associated with them speech etiquette formulas.

This part of the training content constitutes linguistic and cultural studies material, the assimilation of which necessarily requires familiarization with national culture of the people of the language being studied. It is important to emphasize that this “familiarization is carried out through the English language and in the process of its study” [4].

Linguistic and cultural information is used in various exercises – speech, communication.

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION”

International Conference on Teacher Education

An important place among these types of exercises belongs to gaming and situational exercises.

The linguacultural methodology of the English language serves to implement both the main goal of learning - communicative and solving general educational tasks that the methodology faces, which is an organic part of pedagogical science.

Intensifying English language teaching is not only linguistic optimization of the presentation of language material, psychological and other factors play no less important role.

The term pedagogy is used in scientific literature in two meanings: pedagogy as a cycle of psychological and pedagogical sciences and pedagogy as science of education.

The concept of “education” presupposes constant educational influence on the student to the surrounding reality, formation of systems of certain moral and aesthetic qualities, the development views and beliefs, development of individual abilities of students.

Educational influence in the process of teaching English carried out in a system of classroom training and extracurricular activities through their content, which includes both linguistic and regional information.

Learning English, primarily in a non-English audience, is associated with mastering English vocabulary in all its functional and stylistic aspects diversity: mastery of a language without mastery of its lexical richness unthinkable. A huge role in the development of English language learning play various dictionaries, primarily - explanatory, spelling, orthoepic, as well as dictionaries of synonyms, antonyms, homonyms, epithets, i.e. dictionaries related to the display of expressive means of the English language, the richness of its lexical composition.

Great opportunities to implement language, communication, and general educational work is provided by educational texts for independent reading, audiovisual educational materials, television programs and artistic films in English. Modern technique operates qualitatively new ideas, concepts, approaches, at all stages of provision and conduct of the educational process.

Thus, in order to master a foreign language perfectly it is necessary in addition to knowledge of language vocabulary and grammar, also genuine understanding of the interlocutor - a native speaker of another language, knowledge of national psychology, history and way of life of another nation. Only in this way one can achieve that deep mutual understanding, without which cooperation, which all people of good will so strive for, is unthinkable [5].

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION”

International Conference on Teacher Education

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